

Physico-chemical Study of the reaction between heavy metals and chromithiocyanate: Part I. Thallous Chromithiocyanate

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Potassium chromithiocyanate solution forms coloured precipitates with a no. of metallic salt solutions in neutral and acidic medium. Thermometric and conductometric titrations confirm the composition of thallous chromithiocyanate as $Tl_3[Cr(SCN)_6]$.

Roesler¹ prepared $M_3[Cr(SCN)_6] \cdot XH_2O$ from chrome alum and alkali thiocyanates. The Ag, Pb and Ba salts were obtained similarly. Dubsy and Wengenhof² obtained $K_3[Cr(SCN)_6] \cdot 4H_2O$ dark violet cubic crystals and $(NH_4)_3[Cr(SCN)_6] \cdot 4H_2O$ pale-violet cubic crystals. Tsamados³ synthesised chromium thiocyanate complexes of Sn, As and Cd. In the present communication an attempt has been made to throw some light on the composition and nature of thallous chromithiocyanate thermometrically and conductometrically.

EXPERIMENTAL

Potassium chromithiocyanate was prepared and standardised by methods adopted by Roesler¹ and Bjerrum⁴. Pure or A. R. (B.D.H.) quality chemicals were used.

Thermometric Study: The thermometric titrations were carried out in aqueous and aqueous-alcoholic medium. The total corrected rise in temperature was plotted graphically as the function of the volume of the titrant. The arrangement of thermometric titration was the same as employed by Bhattacharya and Saxena⁵. In each titration only one maximum or point of interaction has been observed. The results of thermometric titrations have been given in Table 1 (Curves 1 to 6 in Fig. 1A and Curves 7 to 12 in Fig. 1B).

Conductometric Study: The conductivity was measured by Searfass Conductivity Bridge, Model RCM 15 B1, at $25^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$. The difference in specific conductance against the fraction $[Tl_2SO_4] / \{[Cr(SO_4)_3]^{-3} + [Tl_2SO_4]\}$ was plotted. Using equimolar solutions (M/50, M/100 & M/200) each of thallous sulphate and potassium chromithiocyanate, the stoichiometry of the compound (salt) comes to 1.5:1 (curves A to C in Fig. 2).

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2. *Chem. Obzor*, 1940, 15, 217; *Chem. Zentr*, 1941, 1, 5199.

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Tl_2SO_4 in ml.
FIG. 1A.

$K_2Cr(SCN)_6$ in ml.
FIG. 1B

FIG. 2

TABLE I

I. Direct Titrations:		Ti_2SO_4 reqd. for (v) ml. of M/15 $K_2Cr(SCN)_6$ in ml. (V_1).	Ti_2SO_4 Calculated for (v) ml. of M/15 $K_2Cr(SCN)_6$ (V_2).	Difference between V_1 & V_2 .	Curve No.
M/15 $K_2Cr(SCN)_6$ taken in ml. (v).	Alcohol added in ml.				
30.0	0.0	9.5	9.0	0.5	1 M/3 Ti_2SO_4 and M/15
27.0	3.0	8.5	8.0	0.4	2 $K_2Cr(SCN)_6$; Mole-
24.0	6.0	7.5	7.2	0.3	3 cular ratio (n)=5:1
30.0	0.0	19.0	18.0	1.0	4 M/6 Ti_2SO_4 and M/15
27.0	3.0	16.8	16.2	0.6	5 $K_2Cr(SCN)_6$; Mole-
24.0	6.0	14.6	14.4	0.4	6 cular ratio (n)=5:2

II. Reverse Titrations:		$K_2Cr(SCN)_6$ reqd. for (v) ml. of M/10 Ti_2SO_4 in ml. (V_1).	$K_2Cr(SCN)_6$ calculated for (v) ml. of M/10 Ti_2SO_4 in ml. (V_2).	Difference between V_1 & V_2 .	Curve No.
M/1 Ti_2SO_4 taken in ml. (v).	Alcohol added in ml.				
30.0	0.0	9.4	10.0	0.6	7 M/5 $K_2Cr(SCN)_6$ and
27.0	3.0	8.6	9.0	0.4	8 M/10 Ti_2SO_4 ; Mole-
24.0	6.0	7.7	8.0	0.3	9 cular ratio (n)=2:1
30.0	0.0	20.0	20.0	0.0	10 M/10 $K_2Cr(SCN)_6$.
27.0	3.0	18.0	18.0	0.0	11 and M/10 Ti_2SO_4
24.0	6.0	16.0	16.0	0.0	12 Molecular ratio(n)=1:1

DISCUSSION

In direct titrations the observed titre values of Tl_2SO_4 in aq. medium are higher than the calculated values of Tl_2SO_4 ; while the observed titre values of $K_3 Cr (SCN)_6$ are lower than the theoretical values when the titrations are carried in aq. medium by the reverse way. The difference between the observed and the theoretical titre values in the direct and reverse titrations can be explained on the basis of hydrolytic and adsorptive nature of the precipitated compound. On hydrolysis thalious chromithiocyanate would give some $Cr(SCN)_6^{3-}$ which would consume some extra Tl^+ ions leading to higher titre value.

The adsorption of Tl^+ and $Cr (SCN)_6^{3-}$ ions by the precipitated thalious chromithiocyanate may also bring about the discrepancy in the observed titre values from the calculated ones. In presence of increasing amount of alcohol the adsorption is checked to some extent leading the titre values closer to the theoretical amounts.

In conductometric titrations only one maximum in each case has been observed, confirming the composition of thalious chromithiocyanate as $Tl_3 [Cr(SCN)_6]$. Thalious chromithiocyanate is dirty white coloured powder, practically insoluble in water, alcohols, CCl_4 , ether, CS_2 , esters, ketones and dil. fatty and mineral acids. But it is soluble in saturated hypo and alkali solution.

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